

Table 1. Grain quality performance of Xiangyou 63.

Hybrid/ standard	Institutes ^a doing the testing (year)	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Kernel		Chalkiness		Gelatinization temperature (alkali value)	Gel consistency (mm)	Amylose content (%)	Protein content (%)
					Length (mm)	L-W ratio	Rice (%)	Area (%)				
Xiangyou 63	HRRRI (1988)	81.6	73.0	64.0			24.2	7.4				
	CNRRI (1990)	80.7	72.5	38.1 ^b	7.0	3.0	51 ^b	9.1	6.4	54	22	7.55
	SGBA (1992)	82.6	71.4		7.03	3.0		3.0		40	20.6	8.6
Chinese Ministry of Agriculture standard	1st class	>81	>74	>59	6.5-7.5	>3.0	<5	<5	>4	>60	17-22	>8
	2nd class	>79	>72	>54	5.6-6.5	2.5-3.0	<10	<10	24	41-60	<25	>8

^aHRRRI = Hunan Rice Research Institute, CNRRI = Chinese National Rice Research Institute, and SGAB = Shaoguan Agricultural Bureau. ^bXiangyou 63 did not mature very well in 1990 because of late sowing, which gave lower head rice and higher chalky rice percentages than the other results.

Table 2. Agronomic characters of Xianyou 63. Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trial, China, 1988.

Hybrid	Locations (no.)	Hybrids tested (no.)	Replica- tions (no.)	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets/ panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1,000- grain weight (g)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Xiangyou 63	15	10	3	126	99	91.9	81.1	28.1	6.7 ns
Weiyou 6 (check)	15	10	3	127	88	94.5	80.4	26.6	6.6

^ans = yields not significant by Duncan's SSR test.

Rice Variety Regional Trials, it yielded a mean 6.8 t/ha with a growth duration of 126 d, which was comparable with that of check Weiyou (Table 2). It has also been cultivated in farmers' fields and grown in demonstration plots in 19 provinces in

China. For example, as a single crop grown on 23.5 ha in Bingchuan, Yunnan, in 1994, it yielded 11.9 t/ha.

The hybrid was evaluated for blast resistance in Hunan. It scored 4, 4, and 0 for seedling, leaf, and neck blast, respectively,

on the 1-9 scales of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. It had good field resistance to rice blast and bacterial leaf blight.

Xiangyou 63 has wide adaptability and can be grown as either a late crop in the double rice-cropping areas on which Weiyou 6 is commonly planted, or as a single crop in the single rice-cropping areas planted to Shanyou 63, the most popular hybrid in China. When planted as late rice in the double-cropping system in Hunan, it was about 100 cm tall with strong tillering ability. Its seed set was more than 75% with a mean of 100 spikelets/panicle and a 1,000-grain weight of 28 g. ■

Zhushan A: a new Honglian-type cytoplasmic male sterile line with good grain quality

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Grain quality is one of the important objectives in hybrid rice breeding. The poor grain quality of leading cytoplasmic male

sterile (CMS) lines, such as Zhenshan 97 A and V20A, has contributed to retarding the production of high-quality hybrid rices in China. Our goal was to breed high-quality CMS lines to improve the grain quality of hybrid rice.

In 1982 autumn, high-quality variety Shuangzhuzhan was used as the maternal parent in a cross with wild rice S7539 (*O. sativa* f. *spontanea*), which has multiple pest resistances. The F₁ generation was

crossed with bacterial blight-resistant cultivar Gushan in 1983 spring. The best line, Zhushan, was developed from this multiple cross in 1986. From 1987 spring onward, Zhushan was used as the recurrent parent in a backcross to Guang 41 A, a new Honglian-type CMS line. Zhushan A, a new Honglian-type CMS line, was bred in 1991.

We conducted a series of experiments under irrigated lowland conditions in Zhanjiang (N21°10') during 1991-93 to

Table 1. Heading date, fertility, and general combining ability (GCA) effects for grain quality characters of Zhushan A, Zhenshan 97 A, and Guang 41 A. Zhangjiang, China. 1991-93.

CMS line ^a	Trait								
	Days to heading ^b	Fertility (%)			Relative value of GCA effects (%) ^c				
		Pollen	Stained sterile pollen	Spikelet	Chalkiness ^d	Length ^e (cm)	Width ^f (cm)	Length-width ratio	Milling rate of polished head rice (%)
Zhushan A	78 ± 12	0-0.1	9.7-63.3	0-0.2	-10.3* ^g	3.9*	-8.3**	12.6**	3.2**
Zhenshan 97 A (check)	69 ± 12	0-0.1	3.0- 6.8	0-0.1	7.2** ^g	-1.5	6.0**	-7.15	-1.4
Guang 41 A (check)	86 ± 16	0-0.1	8.2-55.1	0-0.1	3.1*	-2.4	2.3	-5.5	-1.8
SE for GCA value					1.3	1.6	2.0	4.5	1.2

^aZhenshan 97 A is a leading wild abortive CMS line in China. Guang 41 A is a leading Honglian-type CMS line in Guangdong Province, China. ^bMean values across 16 seeding times from 3 Feb to 13 Aug 1992. ^cThe six restorer lines, R59, R56, R892, Zaoteqing, Gujinyang, and 771, that can restore the fertility of both Honglian-type and wild abortive-type CMS lines were used in an incomplete diallel experiment. ^dMeasured using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^eSum of the length of 10 brown rice grains. ^fSum of the width of 10 brown rice grains. ^g*, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively.

observe the traits of Zhushan A, to test its general combining ability (GCA) effects on some grain quality characters, and to determine the yield capacity of the new hybrids from Zhushan A.

Zhushan A has good plant type and is about 85 cm tall. It has dark green leaves, erect flag leaves, and long-slender grain (9.1 mm long × 2.6 mm wide). Its heading date was 78 d, which was 9 d longer than that of Zhenshan 97 A and 8 d shorter than that of Guang 41 A (Table 1). Pollen fertility was 0-0.1%. Like the Honglian-type CMS line Guang 41 A, Zhushan A had 9.7-63.3% stained sterile pollen. The sterility of Zhushan A is acceptable for commercial hybrid rice production in southern China.

In a 3 × 6 incomplete diallel experiment, the relative values of GCA effects of the parents were estimated by Bulmer's method. Zhushan A had higher GCA effects for grain length, length-width ratio, and milling rate of polished head rice than did Zhenshan 97 A and Guang 41 A, but lower GCA effects for chalkiness and grain width. Therefore, Zhushan A could be used to produce hybrids with lower chalkiness, grain length, grain width, length-width ratio in grain, and milling rates of polished head rice (Table 1).

Yield trials were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Four of the hybrid crosses from Zhushan A yielded 8.0-8.4 t/ha during the early cropping season (5.6-10.7% more than the national check Shanyou 63) and 6.9-7.1 t/ha during the late cropping season (2.5-5.4% more than the provincial check Shanyou 64) (Table 2). For the four hybrids, grain length was 6.1-6.8 mm; length-width ratio, 2.5-3.2; chalkiness, 0-1; amylose content, 19.7-23.5%; and grain quality, grade 1 or 2. In the 1993 early cropping season, Zhuyou 61 (Zhushan A/R61) yielded 7.7 t/ha, ranking first among 14 crosses in the united test of high-quality hybrid rice of southern China. Zhuyouqing (Zhushan A/Meiqing) ranked second in a regional test during the early cropping season in Guangdong Province.

Zhushan A has greater GCA for grain quality characters than do other CMS lines. The hybrid crosses derived from Zhushan A have good grain quality and higher grain yield, making the line valuable for use in breeding programs. ■

Table 2. Grain yield and grain quality of several Zhushan A hybrids. Zhanjiang, China. 1991-93 early and late cropping seasons.^a

Character	Hybrid							
	Zhushan A/Meiqing		Zhushan A/R61		Zhushan A/R903		Zhushan A/R54	
	Early	Late	Early	Late	Early	Late	Early	Late
Grain yield (t/ha)	8.0	7.1	8.2	7.0	8.3	7.0	8.4	6.9
Check ^b	5.6	5.4	8.1 ^c	4.0	8.7*	3.7	10.7**	2.5
Grain quality								
Grain length (mm)	6.1	6.7	6.5	6.8	6.6	6.8	6.4	6.6
Length-width ratio	2.5	2.7	2.7	3.0	3.0	3.2	2.8	3.1
Chalkiness	0-1	0-1	0-1	0-1	0-1	0-1	0-1	0-1
Amylose content (%)	22.0	21.1	23.5	21.0	20.8	21.3	19.7	21.8
Quality grade ^d	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	1

^a Early crop was seeded in February, late crop was seeded in July. ^b Shanyou 63 was the check for the early crop and Shanyou 64 for the late crop. ^c *, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ^d According to the national standard of high-quality rice in China, quality grade 1 = milling rate of brown rice >81% and that of polished rice >72%, half-transparent rice grain, length-width ratio is >3.0, and amylose content = 17-22%. Quality grade 2 = milling rate of brown rice >79% and that of polished rice >72%, half-transparent rice grain, length-width ratio = 2.5-3.0, and amylose content <25%.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Turant Dhan: a very early rice variety released in Bihar, India

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Flood or drought periodically affects rice in Bihar—especially in the northern areas. Sometimes floods and droughts occur at the same time in different parts of the state. Farmers require rice varieties that are suitable for pre-flood and post-flood conditions and for intermittent drought to enable a harvest on the available rainfall.

Varieties that are very early-maturing are the obvious choice for these situations. Sattari, Prasana, and Heera, which all have 70-75 d durations and were released in recent years, have not been accepted by farmers because of their poor yield and susceptibility to diseases and insect pests.

We began working to develop very early rice varieties in the early 1980s. Numerous early-maturing cultures from IRRI were evaluated. A hybridization program was undertaken that made use of available very early germplasm.

Culture ES18-5-1, with 70-75 d duration, was developed from the cross Sattari/Rasi. The culture consistently outyielded

Table 1. Yields of ES18-5-1 in uniform varietal trials at different locations in Bihar, India. 1989-95.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha) (pre-flood)					
		ES18-5-1	Sattari	Prasana	Heera	CV (%)	LSD (5%)
1989-90	Dhangain	3.1	2.3	1.4	—	12.6	0.4
	Pusa	2.4	1.7	1.9	—	16.0	0.6
1990-91	Dhangain	2.8	2.7	2.1	—	11.9	0.8
	Sabour	2.2	1.9	1.2	—	19.9	0.4
1991-92	Pusa	2.0	1.2	1.7	—	8.8	0.2
	Dhangain	3.1	2.2	1.1	—	15.4	0.3
	Sabour	2.3	1.6	1.3	—	14.6	0.6
1992-93	Pusa	1.3	1.1	1.2	—	13.1	0.2
	Dhangain	2.1	2.5	1.6	0.6	ns ^a	
	Sabour	1.9	1.2	1.0	1.1	11.1	0.2
1993-94	Pusa	2.6	1.8	1.2	0.9	10.4	0.4
	Bikramganj	4.3	4.3	1.1	1.7	13.9	0.1
	Sabour	1.5	1.1	1.1	0.5	16.8	0.8
	Pusa	3.8	3.0	2.7	2.3	11.8	0.05
1994-95	Patna	1.6	2.3	1.4	0.5	ns	
	Pusa	2.9			2.0	13.8	0.6
	Pooled mean	2.5	2.0	1.5	1.2		

^ans = not significant.